

ISSUES OF STUDYING THE HISTORY OF KARAKALPAKSTAN IN FOREIGN HISTORICAL STUDY

G. Asanova
Teacher at KSU academic lyceum

Annotaciya: Biz bul maqalamızda qaraqalpaqstan tariyxınıń dúnyadaǵı tariyx ilimleri sheńberinde úyreniliwin bir neshe ilimiy ádebiyatlardaǵı kózqaraslarǵa súyene otırıp, izertlewge háreket ettik.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы попытались проанализировать историю Каракалпакстана в области исторических наук в мире, основываясь на взглядах нескольких научных литератур.

Annotation: In this article, we tried to analyze the history of Karakalpakstan in the field of historical sciences in the world, based on the views of several scientific literatures.

Gilt sózler: Qaraqalpaqstan, tariyx, arxeologiya, jáhán tariyxı, derek.

Ключевые слова: Каракалпакстан, история, археология, всемирная история, источник.

Keywords: Karakalpakstan, history, archaeology, world history, source.

One of the most important tasks of the science of history in humanitarian sciences (archaeology, history, philology) in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan is to study and evaluate the literature published abroad on the "History of Karakalpakstan" from the point of view of "historiography".

It is certainly interesting to know what the European, Russian, Turkish and Azerbaijani scientists (archeology, history, eastern researchers, Turkologists, etc.) think and think about the Karakalpkaks.

Most experts are paying attention to foreign literature. Professor M. Mambetullaev and historian O. Yusupov evaluates the information of European and Russian scientists and travelers in the 17th-18th centuries from a "historical" point of view in the scientific article "History of Karakalpakstan in European and Eastern sources".

Professor M. Maxmudov, U. Sharipov have paid attention to the foreign policy of the Russian Empire to the East, the ambassadors sent to the Khiva Khanate, and foreign

information about the occupation of Khiva by Tsarist Russia in their scientific article "The situation of the Khiva Khanate in foreign historiography".

Academician E.V. Rtveladze mentioned the information about "Khiva in foreign historiography". He tells information about the historical literature of the 18th-20th centuries by foreign researchers related to the Southern Aral Sea and the Khanate of Khiva.

Professor B.A. Koshchanov is the first man who paid attention to foreign literature on the "History of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm in the 20th century". He showed the compatibility of information from foreign literature with the information of the archive documents about the expansion policy of the Bolsheviks with the power of the Red Army and the services of the group of "Yosh Xivaliklar" who joined them in 1919-1920 in order to establish the Shuro government in the Amudarya region of the Southern Aral Sea.

William Mendel mentions that the territorial khanate of "Khiva and Bukhara" was influenced by Tsarist Russia and the Bolsheviks, and was subject to it in his information about "Central Asia" (New York). It is said that the Bolsheviks participated in the suspension of the Khiva Khanate together with the "Yosh Xivaliklar".

Richard Pipes says that "in February 1920, the Bolsheviks and the Khiva people" captured the Khiva fortress without any resistance, and the "Yosh Xivaliklar" formed the People's Republic of Khorezm with the help of the Bolsheviks and the Red Army troops in his information about "The structure of the Shura government, the conquest of Muslim regions (Cambridge)".

In the beginning of the 21st century, the information published in English about the history, nature, economy and culture of the South Island in the science of humanitarian history, related to the history, ethnography, toponymy, hydronyms of the Buruu people of the South Aral Sea, from the library of Kent University in the USA by K. Khamidov. He rendered great service in studying the information published in the "Geography" magazine (1876).[1]

"Geography" magazine provides the following information. There is a Lake Aybuyir on the left side of Amudarya along the Southern Aral Sea, between Khodjely and Kungrad. It is said that Tallik river, the Katta river is located in the seaward part of the Amudarya river. The tributaries of the Amudarya on the right (eastern) side are the Kegeyli channel, the Kuanish jarma tributary to the Chimbay border, the right (eastern) side of the Kuanish jarma tributary borders the Kizilkum desert. It was noted that Daukara Lake and Qizil River are located in this region, and Bel mountain is located in the Northern region.

An American scientist and geographer Herbert Wood studied the natural geography of the South Island region, people's lifestyle, culture, towns and cities at the end of the 19th century. Herbert Wood records information about the Karakalpak people in the region on the Amudarya river, the main water supply of the people of the South Aral Sea.

At the beginning of the 21st century, the literature published in Western and Turkish history about the Karakalpaks was analyzed by the scientist M. Qarlibaev, and the data of the ethnologist-historian Peter Golden. [2] Turkish historian Salih Elmaz published about the Karakalpaks in the magazine "Tarix dergishi" (1997). At the beginning of the 21st century, historian Salih Elmaz's information is noteworthy in the field of Turkish history, focusing on the history and culture of the Karakalpak people of the South Aral Sea. (-Salih Ylmaz Karakalpak Turkeri Tarini, XVI- XX yuzyillarda, Ankara, 2005.- Salih Ylmaz Karakalpak Turkleri ve Karakalpakistan Tarixi. Стамбуль, 2008).

Turkish researchers highly appreciate the high culture of Karakalpak history and culture of four hundred years of rich historical past. According to the information of Salih Elmaz, "Karakalpaks had relations with Uzbek khanates and Cossack khanates during the Golden Horde, as part of the Nugai khanate." It also contains information about "protest movements against the tyranny of tsarist Russia and the social policy of the Khiva Khanate". [3.4]

The information of Nizam Mamedov, Professor of Baku University, is particularly noteworthy in the study of the history, culture, literature and folklore of the Karakalpaks of Aral, one of the Turkic peoples of Central Asia at the beginning of the 21st century.

N. Mamedov gave information about the origin, ethnic formation, lifestyle and culture of the Karakalpak people of the Aral Sea, the similarities between the Karakalpak people in Azerbaijan, the Gagaoguz people in Moldavia, and the now-extinct medieval Karakhanid people on the Volga River.

REFERENCES

1. K. Xamidov. Noviy Angloyaziyaniy pis menniy istochnik XIX veka o yujnom poberej`e Arala. Vestnik. №2. 2006, 42-45 p.
2. M. Karlibaev Nekotorie dannie zarubejnoj istoriografii po istorii karakalpakov. Vestnik. N2, 2008, 80-85 p.
3. Yulmar Salin «Karakalpak Turkeri Tarini, XVI- XX yuzyillarda» Ankara, 2006. 4. Salih Ylmaz «Karakalpak Turkleri ve Karakalpakistan Tarixi» Istanbul, 2008.
5. Vambery h. «Reis in Mittelasiien van Teheran durch die Turkmanische Wuste andev ostkuste des Kaspischen Meeres wach chiwa Bachara and Samarqand». 2 verm, Leipring, 1873..